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Buffet boundary estimation using a harmonic balance method

Andrea Petrocchi, George Barakos*

CFD Laboratory, School of Engineering, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, G128QQ, UK

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the application of the harmonic balance technique is demonstrated for transonic buffet cases. The harmonic balance method represents an alternative to time-marching simulations that are expensive for complex flow cases. Here this technique is applied on different test cases with inherently unsteady flows, i.e. two different aerofoil configurations undergoing transonic buffet. A gradient-based, variable time period method is used to estimate the frequency of oscillation for flows where it is not known a priori. The reduced computer costs with respect to time marching simulations allowed to embed the harmonic balance computation in a simple procedure for the buffet boundary estimation. The aim is to improve the prediction coming from criteria based on the results of steady computations, still popular in industry.

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1. Introduction

Transonic buffet is defined as a self-sustained shock oscillation occurring at transonic conditions, and can also become associated with a dynamic structural response. This oscillation may be detrimental in terms of structural integrity or flight controllability. The exact buffet mechanism is not fully understood, and a number of researchers tried to shed light on this, generating and driving the oscillations over aerofoils and wings [1–5]. For an introduction to the topic, the reader is referred to the review paper of Lee [6] and, for recent developments, to the work of Giannelis et al. [7]. The cause of this phenomenon remains unclear and significant efforts have been made towards its understanding.

Therefore, over the past decade, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) has been extensively used to investigate transonic buffet flows. The prediction of this phenomenon by means of time marching simulations (TMS) proved to be challenging, and not consistently accurate. In principle, an unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) approach seemed optimal because of the large time scales associated with the shock oscillations (especially in case of turbulent transonic buffet). Indeed, a number of authors investigated the ability of URANS simulations to predict the buffet for both two- [8–13] and three-dimensional cases [14,15]. Because of the sensitivity to the turbulence modelling, numerical schemes, and spatio-temporal discretisation adopted, no consensus was found in this regard. For this reason, with the recent rise in computer power, increasingly detailed yet expensive computations, spanning from hybrid RANS-LES [16–18,12,19–21] to LES [22–25] and DNS [26], have been used to analyse this class of flows. The main drawback of these methods is the considerably higher CPU costs stemming from the fine spatio-temporal discretisation required.

To avoid costs associated with TMS, engineering criteria have been proposed for the buffet boundary prediction on wings, based on the results of experimental investigations [1,27]. Criteria based on the trailing edge pressure coefficient or the deviation from linear trends of the lift or pitching moment coefficient are the most popular. Chung et al. [28] applied some of these using RANS computations. The CPU costs were limited, and computations of the steady solutions were repeated for several flight conditions. In an earlier work [29], we proposed a method for the efficient estimation of the buffet boundary by means of the aforementioned RANS-based criteria and the adjoint method to further optimise the process of buffet boundary estimation. Nevertheless, the use of buffet criteria is limited to steady computations and their accuracy strongly depends on the employed turbulence model. It is believed that time marching simulations can improve the prediction of the buffet onset, in spite of the large CPU cost associated with them.

When dealing with periodic flows, the use of the frequency domain reduces the CPU costs needed for the several periods of oscillations and the transient needed to reach periodic conditions. Popular methods are the time spectral method [30], the nonlinear frequency domain

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: andrea.petrocchi@glasgow.ac.uk (A. Petrocchi), george.barakos@glasgow.ac.uk (G. Barakos).

Nomenclature

b	threshold for unsteady buffet boundary criterion	α_B	onset angle of attack..... deg
C_p	pressure coefficient $\frac{p - p_\infty}{0.5\rho U_\infty^2}$	ΔM_∞	Mach number increment
C_D	drag coefficient $\frac{D}{0.5\rho U_\infty^2 c}$	ϵ_α	angle of attack tolerance..... deg
C_L	lift coefficient $\frac{L}{0.5\rho U_\infty^2 c}$	ϵ_N	spectral viscosity coefficient
C_μ	model constant	μ	molecular dynamic viscosity..... $\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
D	pseudospectral operator	μ_t	eddy viscosity..... $\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
D_2	temporal spectral viscosity operator	ν_t	kinematic eddy viscosity..... $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
E	Fourier transformation matrix	ω	turbulent frequency..... s^{-1}
E^{-1}	inverse Fourier transformation matrix	Ω	fundamental frequency of oscillation..... s^{-1}
E_{cutoff}	cutoff Fourier transformation matrix	ρ	density..... kg m^{-3}
f_k	unresolved-to-total ratio of turbulent kinetic energy	ρ_i	cutoff coefficient
f_ϵ	unresolved-to-total ratio of turbulent dissipation	τ	pseudo time
f_ω	unresolved-to-total ratio of turbulent frequency	$\beta^*, \beta, \gamma, \sigma_k, \sigma_\omega$	SST model constants
F_1, F_2	SST model blending functions	Acronyms	
J_{imp}	Jacobian matrix	BILU	Block Incomplete Lower-Upper
k	turbulent kinetic energy..... $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$	CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
m	cutoff harmonic	DDES	Delayed Detached-Eddy Simulations
M_∞	Mach number	DES	Detached-Eddy Simulations
N_H	number of harmonics	GBVTP	Gradient-Based Variable Time Period
N_T	number of sub-intervals in a period of oscillation	GCG	Generalised Conjugate Gradient
P_k	turbulent kinetic energy production term. $\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-3}$	GMRES	Generalised Minimum Residual
\mathbf{R}	flow residual vector	HB	Harmonic Balance
Re_c	Reynolds number $\frac{\rho U_\infty c}{\mu}$	HMB	Helicopter Multi-Block
St	Strouhal number $\frac{kc}{U_\infty}$	IDDES	Improved Delayed Detached-Eddy Simulations
t	time..... s	LES	Large-Eddy Simulations
T	period of oscillation..... s	MUSCL	Monotone Upstream-centred Scheme for Conservation Laws
U_i	flow velocity..... m s^{-1}	PANS	Partially Averaged Navier-Stokes
$V_{i,j,k}$	cell volume	RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
x_i	spatial coordinates..... m	SAS	Scale-Adaptive Simulations
\mathbf{W}	flow variable vector	SBLI	Shock-Wave/Boundary-Layer Interaction
α	angle of attack..... deg	SST	Shear Stress Tensor
		TMS	Time-Marching Simulation
		TSV	Time Spectral Viscosity
		URANS	Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes

method [31], and the harmonic balance (HB) [32] method. The latter has been widely used to study turbomachinery [32,33] and rotor flows [34], where the frequency of the periodic flow is known *a priori*. Self-induced, unsteady flows, like vortex shedding or transonic buffet flows, introduce a problem related to the lack of knowledge of the fundamental flow frequency. So far, although several, successful attempts were made regarding the first category [30,35,36], the only application of spectral methods for transonic buffet is attributed to Plante and Laurendeau [36]. They used a time spectral method to simulate the transonic buffet around the OAT15A aerofoil, using the gradient-based variable time period (GBVTP) method of McMullen et al. [31] to evaluate the buffet frequency starting from a guess value.

In this paper, we assess the ability of the harmonic balance method implemented in the HMB3 solver of the University of Glasgow to cope with transonic buffet flows. The method is then used within a procedure to estimate the buffet boundary for two-dimensional configurations with data available from experiments.

This paper is structured as follows: the mathematical model and the algorithm used to estimate the buffet boundary are presented in sec. 2; sec. 3 sees the results of TMS and HB computations for the test cases under analysis; sec. 4 is devoted to discussion and conclusions.

2. Numerical method

2.1. Computational model for fluid flow

Numerical simulations have been performed using the Helicopter Multi-Block (HMB3) [37,38] flow solver, a three-dimensional, fully implicit, structured, multi-block code for the solution of the Navier-Stokes equations. The Navier-Stokes equations are discretised using a cell-centred finite volume approach. The computational domain is divided into a finite number of non-overlapping control volumes, and the governing equations are applied to each cell in turn. Also, the Navier-Stokes equations are re-written in a curvilinear co-ordinate system which simplifies the formulation of the discretised terms since body-conforming grids are adopted here. The spatial discretisation of equations leads to a set of ordinary differential equations in time,

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\mathbf{W}_{ijk} V_{ijk}) = -\mathbf{R}_{ijk}(\mathbf{W}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{R} are the vectors of cell conserved variables and residuals, respectively, and V is the cell volume. The convective terms are discretised using Osher's upwind scheme [39]. A monotone upstream-centred scheme for conservation laws (MUSCL) variable extrapolation [40] is used to provide second-order accuracy with the Van Albada limiter [41] to prevent spurious oscillations around shock waves. For the integration in time, the implicit dual-time stepping method of Jameson [42] is used.

The linearised system of equations is solved using the generalised conjugate gradient (GCG) method with a block incomplete lower-upper (BILU) factorisation as a pre-conditioner [43]. The Jacobian is approximated by evaluating the derivatives of the residuals with a first-order scheme for the inviscid fluxes. The first-order Jacobian requires less storage and ensures a better convergence rate to the GCG iterations. The steady-state solver for turbulent flows is formulated and solved in an identical manner to that of the mean flow. The eddy-viscosity is calculated from the latest values of the turbulent variables, e.g. k and ω , and is used to advance the mean and the turbulent flow solutions. An approximate Jacobian is used for the source term of the models by only taking into account the contribution of their dissipation terms, i.e. no account of the production terms is taken on the left-hand side of the system. In this work, a PANS formulation was adopted, and it is described in the following paragraph.

2.2. PANS formulation

The partially-averaged Navier-Stokes (PANS) formulation [44] is a bridging model between RANS and DNS. The formulation is based on a RANS paradigm, where the blending is obtained by means of the user-prescribed unresolved-to-total ratios of turbulent kinetic energy f_k and dissipation f_ϵ , bounded between 0 and 1, acting on the turbulence closure equations. They read: $f_k = k_u/k$, $f_\epsilon = \epsilon_u/\epsilon$, where the u subscripts stand for unresolved and the quantities at the denominator are the total ones. The PANS method was initially derived for k - ϵ closures and then extended to the Wilcox k - ω model [45] by Lakshmipathy et al. [46] and to the Menter SST model [47] by Luo et al. [48]. In k - ω based formulations the parameter f_ϵ is replaced by the unresolved-to-total turbulence frequency $f_\omega = \omega_u/\omega = f_\epsilon/f_k$. These formulations inherit from the parent RANS models an eddy viscosity based on a Boussinesq approximation, that is reduced with respect to the RANS case because of the effects of the f_k parameter: since only a fraction of the turbulent kinetic energy is modelled, the corresponding value of the eddy viscosity is reduced. This gives the possibility for the turbulent structures to be resolved. When adopting a reasonably high value of f_k , the method can be used as a less dissipative version of URANS.

In this work, the SST-PANS formulation is adopted. It reads

$$\frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho U_j k)}{\partial x_j} = P_k - \beta^* \rho k \omega + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \mu_t \sigma_k \frac{f_\omega}{f_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right], \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \omega)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho U_j \omega)}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\gamma}{\nu_t} P_k - \beta' \rho \omega^2 + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \mu_t \sigma_\omega \frac{f_\omega}{f_k} \right) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right] + 2 \frac{f_\omega}{f_k} (1 - F_1) \frac{\rho \sigma_\omega}{\omega} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j}, \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the density, U_j is the flow velocity, μ is the dynamic molecular viscosity and μ_t is the turbulent viscosity. Here, the turbulent kinetic energy k and frequency ω are the modelled, or unresolved, fraction where the subscripts were dropped for sake of simplicity. In the ω -equation, $\beta' = \left(\gamma \beta^* - \frac{\gamma \beta^*}{f_\omega} + \frac{\beta}{f_\omega} \right)$; F_1 is the blending function while $\gamma, \beta, \beta^*, \sigma_k, \sigma_\omega$ are the model constants, calculated as prescribed in reference [47]. The eddy viscosity has the same form as in the formulation of the SST model.

2.3. Harmonic balance formulation

Here, the harmonic balance formulation is described together with the implementation in HMB3 following the work of Woodgate and Barakos [34]. The harmonic balance method approximates the flow solution and residual vectors in eq. (1) with a Fourier expansion truncated to a specific number of harmonics N_H , after assuming the flow periodicity in time with frequency Ω . The two vectors are, therefore, written as:

$$W(t) = \sum_{k=-N_H}^{N_H} \hat{W}_k e^{ik\Omega t}, \quad (4)$$

$$R(t) = \sum_{k=-N_H}^{N_H} \hat{R}_k e^{ik\Omega t}. \quad (5)$$

Once the discrete Fourier transforms are substituted into eq. (1) and the orthogonality of the Fourier terms is used, an equation for each k is obtained:

$$\Omega k V \hat{W}_k + \hat{R}_k = \Omega A \hat{W}_k + \hat{R}_k = 0, \quad (6)$$

where A is an $N_T \times N_T$ matrix and $N_T = 2N_H + 1$. Eq. (6) is solved following the pseudo-spectral approach of Hall et al. [32], where the equation is transformed back into the time domain. The solution and the residual are split into N_T discrete, equally-spaced sub-intervals over the period $T = 2\pi/\Omega$:

$$W_{hb} = \begin{pmatrix} W(t_0 + \Delta t) \\ W(t_0 + 2\Delta t) \\ \vdots \\ W(t_0 + T) \end{pmatrix}, \quad R_{hb} = \begin{pmatrix} R(t_0 + \Delta t) \\ R(t_0 + 2\Delta t) \\ \vdots \\ R(t_0 + T) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

By introducing a transformation matrix E , such that $\hat{W} = EW_{hb}$ and $\hat{R} = ER_{hb}$, eq. (6) can be recast as:

$$\Omega AEW_{hb} + ER_{hb} = 0. \quad (8)$$

By premultiplying by E^{-1} , the equation can be recast as:

$$\Omega E^{-1}AEW_{hb} + E^{-1}ER_{hb} = \Omega DW_{hb} + R_{hb} = 0 \quad (9)$$

where $D = E^{-1}AE$ is defined as:

$$D_{ij} = \frac{2}{N_T} \sum_{k=1}^{N_T} k \sin(2\pi k(j-i)/N_T). \quad (10)$$

The two matrices E and E^{-1} are defined as:

$$E = \frac{2}{2N+1} \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 \\ \cos(\Omega t_1) & \cos(\Omega t_2) & \cos(\Omega t_3) & \dots & \cos(\Omega t_{2N+1}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cos(N\Omega t_1) & \cos(N\Omega t_2) & \cos(N\Omega t_3) & \dots & \cos(N\Omega t_{2N+1}) \\ \sin(\Omega t_1) & \sin(\Omega t_2) & \sin(\Omega t_3) & \dots & \sin(\Omega t_{2N+1}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sin(N\Omega t_1) & \sin(N\Omega t_2) & \sin(N\Omega t_3) & \dots & \sin(N\Omega t_{2N+1}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

$$E^{-1} = \frac{2}{2N+1} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cos(\Omega t_1) & \dots & \cos(N\Omega t_1) & \sin(\Omega t_1) & \dots & \sin(N\Omega t_1) \\ 1 & \cos(\Omega t_2) & \dots & \cos(N\Omega t_2) & \sin(\Omega t_2) & \dots & \sin(N\Omega t_2) \\ 1 & \cos(\Omega t_3) & \dots & \cos(N\Omega t_3) & \sin(\Omega t_3) & \dots & \sin(N\Omega t_3) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & \cos(\Omega t_{2N+1}) & \dots & \cos(N\Omega t_{2N+1}) & \sin(\Omega t_{2N+1}) & \dots & \sin(N\Omega t_{2N+1}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

The harmonic balance equation is solved by pseudo-time marching, leading to:

$$\frac{dW_{hb}}{d\tau} + \Omega DW_{hb} + R_{hb} = 0. \quad (13)$$

An implicit method is then used in conjunction with an implicit treatment of the source term, as follows:

$$\Omega DW_{hb}^{n+1} = \Omega DW_{hb}^n + \Omega D(\Delta W_{hb}), \quad (14)$$

and the harmonic balance equation is recast in the form:

$$\frac{W_{hb}^{n+1} - W_{hb}^n}{\Delta\tau} = - \left[\Omega DW_{hb}^{n+1} + R_{hb}(W_{hb}^{n+1}) \right]. \quad (15)$$

The Jacobian matrix J_{Imp} reads

$$J_{Imp} = \begin{bmatrix} \left. \frac{\partial R}{\partial W} \right|_{t_0+\Delta t} & \Omega D_{12} & \dots & \Omega D_{1N_T} \\ \Omega D_{21} & \left. \frac{\partial R}{\partial W} \right|_{t_0+2\Delta t} & & \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \\ \Omega D_{N_T 1} & \Omega D_{N_T 2} & & \left. \frac{\partial R}{\partial W} \right|_{t_0+T} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

and the linear system to be solved is then:

$$\left[\frac{V}{\Delta\tau} + J_{Imp} \right] (W_{hb}^{n+1} - W_{hb}^n) = -\Omega DW_{hb}^n - R_{hb}(W_{hb}^n). \quad (17)$$

The system is solved using a Krylov subspace method with BILU factorisation, as mentioned in sec. 2.1.

Temporal Spectral Viscosity

With respect to the implementation of Woodgate and Barakos [34], the second-order temporal spectral viscosity (TSV) term of Huang and Ekici [49] is added in eq. (13). The additional term dampens the contribution associated with high frequency and helps maintain the accuracy of the time spectral solution. The equation now reads:

$$\frac{dW_{hb}}{d\tau} = -R_{hb} - \Omega DW_{hb} + \Omega^2 D_2 W_{hb} = -R_{hb}^*, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\Omega^2 D_2 = \epsilon_N \frac{d^2 E^{-1}}{dt^2} E_{\text{cutoff}}. \quad (19)$$

The ϵ_N is a viscosity coefficient that is usually equal to $1/N_H$ [49]. The matrix E_{cutoff} is defined as:

$$E_{\text{cutoff}} = \frac{2}{2N+1} \begin{bmatrix} 0.5\rho_0 & 0.5\rho_0 & 0.5\rho_0 & 0.5\rho_0 & 0.5\rho_0 \\ \rho_1 \cos(\Omega t_1) & \rho_1 \cos(\Omega t_2) & \rho_1 \cos(\Omega t_3) & \dots & \rho_1 \cos(\Omega t_{2N+1}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_N \cos(N\Omega t_1) & \rho_N \cos(N\Omega t_2) & \rho_N \cos(N\Omega t_3) & \dots & \rho_N \cos(N\Omega t_{2N+1}) \\ \rho_1 \sin(\Omega t_1) & \rho_1 \sin(\Omega t_2) & \rho_1 \sin(\Omega t_3) & \dots & \rho_1 \sin(\Omega t_{2N+1}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_N \sin(N\Omega t_1) & \rho_N \sin(N\Omega t_2) & \rho_N \sin(N\Omega t_3) & \dots & \rho_N \sin(N\Omega t_{2N+1}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

where

$$\rho_i = \begin{cases} 0, & i \leq m \\ 1, & i \geq m \end{cases}, \quad (21)$$

and m is the cut-off harmonic that determines where the additional viscosity is applied. The D_2 matrix can be easily computed through matrix multiplication, and a compact formula, similar to that of D , is obtained:

$$D_{2,ij} = -\frac{2\epsilon_N}{N_T} \sum_{k=1}^{N_T} k^2 \cos(2\pi k(j-i)/N_T). \quad (22)$$

The introduction of the TSV leads to a modification of the implicit Jacobian in eq. (16), now reading:

$$J_{\text{imp}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial R}{\partial W} \Big|_{t_0+\Delta t} & \Omega D_{12} - \Omega^2 D_{2,12} & \dots & \Omega D_{1N_T} - \Omega^2 D_{2,1N_T} \\ \Omega D_{21} - \Omega^2 D_{2,21} & \frac{\partial R}{\partial W} \Big|_{t_0+2\Delta t} & & \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \\ \Omega D_{N_T 1} - \Omega^2 D_{2,N_T 1} & \Omega D_{N_T 2} - \Omega^2 D_{2,N_T 2} & & \frac{\partial R}{\partial W} \Big|_{t_0+T} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (23)$$

where out-of-diagonal terms are introduced after applying the same implicit treatment of eq. (14) to the term $\Omega^2 D_2 W_{hb}$.

Time Period Estimation

The main limitation of the harmonic balance is the need for prior knowledge of the frequency associated with the time periodicity of the flow. While this parameter is usually known, like for flows in turbomachinery and helicopter rotors, for some other problems, like transonic buffet, the main frequency of oscillation is not known a priori and varies with the flight conditions. To overcome this drawback, the adaptive-frequency method called gradient-based variable time period (GBVTP) [31,30] is used in this work. It is assumed that the solution can only converge when the exact frequency is used, while for a wrong initial guess value, the flow residual tends to stall around some value. Therefore, the derivative of the right-hand-side in eq. (18), called R^* , with respect to the time period must become zero at such condition. The derivative is taken on the square of R^* in agreement with the original formulation [31]:

$$\begin{aligned} R_n^{*2} &= \Omega^2 (DW)_n (DW)_n + 2\Omega (DW)_n R(W)_n - 2\Omega (DW)_n (D_2 W)_n \\ &+ R(W)_n R(W)_n - 2\Omega^2 (D_2 W)_n R(W)_n + \Omega^4 (D_2 W)_n (D_2 W)_n \\ &= 4\frac{\pi^2}{T^2} (DW)_n (DW)_n + 4\frac{\pi}{T} (DW)_n R(W)_n - 16\frac{\pi^3}{T^3} (DW)_n (D_2 W)_n \\ &+ R(W)_n R(W)_n - 8\frac{\pi^2}{T^2} (D_2 W)_n R(W)_n + 16\frac{\pi^4}{T^4} (D_2 W)_n (D_2 W)_n. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial R_n^{*2}}{\partial T} &= -8\frac{\pi^2}{T^3} (DW)_n (DW)_n - 4\frac{\pi}{T^2} (DW)_n R(W)_n + 48\frac{\pi^3}{T^4} (DW)_n (D_2 W)_n \\ &+ 16\frac{\pi^2}{T^2} (D_2 W)_n R(W)_n - 64\frac{\pi^4}{T^5} (D_2 W)_n (D_2 W)_n. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Here, the n subscript refers to the n -th time sample and the hb subscripts were dropped for simplicity. After averaging the gradient over the number of time instances and cells of the computational domain, the time period is updated using:

$$T^{n+1} = T^n - \Delta T \frac{\partial R_n^2}{\partial T}, \quad (26)$$

where ΔT is a constant gain and the time period correction is limited to a constant value to limit the instability of the algorithm due to drastic changes in the associated frequency Ω , updated together with the time period. Doing this, the solution and time period are simultaneously updated. To make the computation even more stable the time period correction can be applied once every user-prescribed number of iterations of the CFD solver.

Fig. 1. Algorithm used for tracing the buffet boundary.

2.4. Algorithm for buffet boundary estimation

Here, the simple algorithm used to trace the buffet boundary is illustrated. In the current study of the buffet boundary, we will only account for Mach number and angle of attack changes. A third parameter like the Reynolds number can also be accounted for but it would increase the required CPU time.

The Mach number is an important parameter in defining the flight conditions and we opted to keep it fixed and evaluate the buffet onset in terms of the angle of attack. The opposite is also possible. The range of flight conditions we are interested in is represented by an interval of Mach numbers $M_{\infty} \in (M_{\infty,A}, M_{\infty,B})$. The flow chart of the algorithm, implemented in MATLAB, is shown in 1. The procedure begins with the definition of an interval of Mach numbers of interest and an initial point $(\alpha_A, M_{\infty,A})$. There, a time marching simulation is carried out to acquire the reduced frequency associated with the buffet motion. Alternatively, a first harmonic balance computation can be carried out with an estimated value for the reduced frequency. This latter way is not as safe as the first because it is not possible to check the exactness of the reduced frequency found using the GBVTP method. Moreover, an incorrect initial guess for the frequency may

Fig. 2. Evolution of the lift coefficient associated with each snapshot of the 1-mode harmonic balance computation at different angles of attack for the OAT15A aerofoil at $M_\infty = 0.73$ and $Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$.

prevent the harmonic balance equations from converging. In particular, if the value is way too low, the GBVTP method may point towards a solution with multiple oscillations (see [36]). Therefore, in this study, a preliminary time-marching simulation was always performed. It is also important that the initial flow conditions correspond to a buffet flow so that the harmonic balance computation for the next step of the procedure starts from a buffet solution. If the initial time marching fails to predict buffet, the angle of attack must be varied until buffet conditions are reached. The state of the boundary layer can be used to decide whether the angle of attack should be increased or decreased. If the boundary layer downstream of the shock is not separated from the shock foot to the trailing edge, the angle of attack must be increased to cross the lower buffet boundary, referred as *buffet onset* for a certain Mach number. An increase in the angle of attack should favour the merging of the two distinct separated regions at the shock foot, and at the trailing edge, into a unique one. If the boundary layer is fully separated and no buffet is present, the aerofoil is likely to be above the upper buffet boundary, *buffet offset* [50], and the angle of attack must be decreased.

After computing the fundamental frequency, the harmonic computation at the same conditions is initialised. As suggested by Plante and Laurendeau [36], we initialise the computation by imposing an oscillation and acquiring the initial snapshots. After that, the aerofoil is kept steady and the frequency is maintained the same. After some iterations, the GBVTP method is activated. If the pitching motion is not prescribed, the harmonic balance computation starts from identical snapshots and moves towards a steady solution. This justifies the need for a buffeting flow as the initial point of the procedure. In this work, a 5 deg oscillation was imposed in all cases. This value was high enough, for the considered cases, to obtain different initial solutions.

After the first harmonic balance computation, the final frequency is acquired and used as the initial guess for the next computation. At any iteration, the exactness of the frequency evaluated through the adaptive frequency method is assessed by looking at the ratio between the final and initial period of oscillation. Indeed, if this ratio is closer to 2 (or bigger integers) than to 1, it means that the solution has two (or more) buffet periods and the computed frequency is incorrect. This is more likely to happen, according to Plante and Laurendeau [36], when starting from a low guess value with respect to the actual one. According to the study of Giannelis et al. [51], this can happen when increasing either Mach number or angle of attack. If the check detects an anomaly in the frequency estimation, the time spectral viscosity is increased to increase the stability of the GBVTP method.

At each iteration, the extracted loads are analysed to determine if there is buffet, corresponding to:

$$\frac{\Delta C_L}{\langle C_L \rangle} \geq b, \quad (27)$$

where ΔC_L is the amplitude of the oscillation in the lift coefficient, $\langle C_L \rangle$ is the mean lift coefficient, and b is some user-prescribed percentage. A value of 5-10% is recommended to avoid considering as buffet, oscillations in the loads due to other factors like vortex shedding for aerofoils with blunt trailing edge, etc.

If the flow is buffeting, the angle of attack is reduced by a user-prescribed amount (the accuracy we need in estimating the buffet boundary) and a new HB computation is performed until a steady solution is reached. An example of how the procedure works is given in Fig. 2, showing the loads associated with each snapshot of a single-mode harmonic balance computation around the OAT15A aerofoil, for different angles of attack. Once the loads have converged, the angle of attack was gradually decreased until steady conditions were reached. In this case, an angle of attack of $\alpha = 3.0$ deg coincided with absence of buffet and, therefore, we could locate the buffet onset for $\alpha_B \in [3.0, 3.1)$. The procedure is repeated until the Mach number falls out of the interval of interest. If this is the case, the Mach number is modified and the angle of attack and frequency are set to the ones of the last buffeting solution. We concluded that it is advisable to proceed by increasing the Mach number (by a fixed user-prescribed amount). Since for conventional configurations the buffet boundary is crossed by increasing either Mach number or angle of attack, to move towards smaller Mach number, an increment of the angle of attack is also required to avoid crossing the buffet boundary. Also, increasing, at the same time both flight parameters may not be enough to avoid this inconvenience. Moreover, a change in both of them will require more time for the HB computation to converge.

3. Application example

3.1. Case description and numerical setup

NACA0012 Wing Section

The first test section analysed, the NACA0012 section, was studied at the Ames High Reynolds Number Facility by McDevitt and Okuno [52]. Mach numbers are in the range of 0.71-0.8 and Reynolds number span between 1 and 10 million. The buffet onset was

Fig. 3. Computational grids adopted in the computations. Left: NACA0012 aerofoil; right: OAT15A aerofoil. The red lines represent the boundaries of the multi-block domain. (For interpretation of the colours in the figure(s), the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

detected by means of steady and unsteady pressure measurements. The tunnel walls were adapted to follow the free air streamlines, while the sidewall interference was reduced by thinning the sidewall boundary layer by means of suction applied on porous panels. Further details are given in the reference. Although these experiments are more than 30 years old, they still represent the broadest database for buffet onset, covering a wide range of conditions. Therefore, the available data were useful to test the performance of the full procedure for the buffet boundary estimation over a larger variety of flight conditions. Moreover, the treatment of the wind tunnel wall allowed considering the flow as close as possible to a perfectly 2D flow, making this test case particularly suitable for this study.

The computational grids used for the aerofoils have a typical C-H topology. The 2D grid consists of 352 cells around the aerofoil, 112 cells in the normal direction, and 104 cells in the wake, for a total of about 62 thousand cells over the domain extending $80c$ both ahead of the aerofoil, and in the wake direction. The spatial distribution has been set to satisfy the condition of $\Delta y^+ < 1$ at each condition, resulting in a first cell size of about $2.0 \times 10^{-6}c$. The grid used for computations (see Fig. 3, left) was selected after carrying out a mesh sensitivity study (see sec. 3.2). Adiabatic wall boundary conditions were imposed at the aerofoil, and free-stream values of pressure and velocity elsewhere. For the time-marching computations, a timestep of $\Delta t = 0.01c/U_\infty$, corresponding to around 1200 steps for each buffet period at $M_\infty = 0.72$ and 6.0 deg, was employed. The convergence of the implicit scheme was based on the reduction of the summation of the conserved flow variables residual with respect to the previous step. In particular, either 3 orders of magnitude of reduction or 100 inner iterations were reached for each unsteady step.

OAT15A Wing Section

The second aerofoil configuration is the supercritical OAT15A wing section, analysed in the S3Ch wind tunnel at ONERA [53,4]. The wing section has a chord of $c = 0.23\text{m}$ and a span, coinciding with that of the tunnel, of 0.78m . The section has a thickness-to-chord ratio of $t/c = 0.123$ and a trailing edge thickness of 0.5% of the chord. The wing was mounted in a squared section wind tunnel having nominal dimensions of $0.78\text{m} \times 0.78\text{m} \times 2.2\text{m}$. An adaptation technique based on a steady flow hypothesis was used at the lower and upper walls to reproduce free-stream conditions. Measurements were collected at free-stream Mach numbers in the range of 0.7 - 0.75 , a chord-based Reynolds number of $Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$ and angles of attack in the range of 1.36 - 3.9 deg. The adoption of static pressure measurements and Kulite sensors distributed in the vicinity of the mid-span section allowed the detection of flow unsteadiness at an angle of attack of 3.1 deg at $M_\infty = 0.73$ and 3.5 deg at $M_\infty = 0.72$. For the case at $M_\infty = 0.73$ and $\alpha = 3.5$ deg, a laser Doppler velocimetry (LDV) system was used to acquire velocity-field data and compute statistics. Although a large characterisation of the buffet onset was provided, the available data was used to assess the exactness of the time-marching simulation for the documented buffet flow.

The numerical setup is the same as that for the NACA0012 aerofoil. The employed grid (see Fig. 3, right) now amounts to 66 thousand cells because of the blunt trailing edge and was selected after a mesh convergence study, analogous to the previous case (see sec. 3.2). The time step employed corresponds to at least 1500 steps for each buffet period for the flight conditions analysed.

3.2. Grid convergence study

To guarantee grid convergence for the geometries under analysis three different grids were tested for flow conditions before and after the buffet onset.

NACA0012

Three different grids consisting of 44, 62, and 84 thousand cells, respectively, were tested using the SST model for the steady flow at $Re_c = 6 \times 10^6$, $M_\infty = 0.778$ and $\alpha = 2.0$ deg around the NACA0012 aerofoil. Fig. 4, left, shows the pressure coefficient distribution around the aerofoil. A slight difference in the pressure level at the suction side reflects in a difference on the third decimal digit in both the lift and drag coefficients (tab. 1). The study was repeated at $Re_c = 1 \times 10^7$, $M_\infty = 0.72$ and $\alpha = 6.0$, i.e., according to the experiments, at buffet conditions. Although the difference is irrelevant for the steady case, for the buffet case the medium and fine grids differ from the coarse one in terms of the amplitude of oscillation (Fig. 4, right). In order to avoid a late buffet onset, the medium grid was selected as the reference one for this study. Using a finer grid does not result in any significant changes in both the predicted amplitude and frequency of oscillation. The buffet reduced frequency was also in agreement with the experimental value.

Fig. 4. Left: pressure coefficient distribution around the NACA0012 aerofoil at $Re_c = 6 \times 10^6$, $M_\infty = 0.778$ and $\alpha = 2.03$ deg, with zoom on the shock region; right: Lift coefficient history for the flow at $Re_c = 1 \times 10^7$, $M_\infty = 0.72$ and $\alpha = 6.0$.

Table 1

Grid convergence study for the NACA0012. C_L , C_D refers to the steady case, while k_B , ΔC_L to the buffet case.

Grid	N_x	N_y	N_{wake}	C_L	C_D	k_B	ΔC_L
Coarse	280	92	92	0.3719	0.0231	0.553	0.1115
Medium	352	112	104	0.3752	0.0224	0.546	0.4159
Fine	416	128	120	0.3757	0.0223	0.545	0.4213
Exp.	-	-	-	-	-	0.55	-

Fig. 5. Left: pressure coefficient distribution around the OAT15A aerofoil at $Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$, $M_\infty = 0.73$ and $\alpha = 2.5$ deg, with zoom on the shock region; right: Lift coefficient history for the flow at $Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$, $M_\infty = 0.73$ and $\alpha = 3.5$.

Table 2

Grid convergence study for the OAT15A. C_L , C_D refers to the steady case, while St , ΔC_L to the buffet case.

Grid	N_x	N_y	N_{wake}	N_{TE}	C_L	C_D	St	ΔC_L
Coarse	280	92	92	41	0.9478	0.0402	0.068	0.2249
Medium	352	112	104	41	0.9519	0.0235	0.067	0.2307
Fine	416	128	120	51	0.9513	0.0235	0.067	0.2332
Exp.	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.066	-

OAT15A

The mesh sensitivity study was carried out in a similar way to the other configuration used. In this case, the flow conditions were $Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$, $M_\infty = 0.73$ and $\alpha = 2.5, 3.5$, with angles of attack corresponding to non-buffeting and buffeting flows, respectively. Similar considerations can be done for the steady case (Fig. 5, left), where the SST model was used to close the equations. Indeed, the grid refinement is irrelevant. For the unsteady case (Fig. 5, right), the grid refinement did not affect significantly the prediction of the amplitude and frequency of the shock oscillation (see tab. 2). Therefore, the medium grid was chosen to be consistent with the previous case. Although small discrepancies with the experiments are seen, the overall agreement allows for carrying out the following studies.

3.3. TMS results

Here the results of the time marching simulations for each test case are briefly discussed. The main scope is to assess the ability of the simulation strategies adopted to correctly predict unsteady flows.

Table 3
Table of time-marching computations performed for the NACA0012 aerofoil, $Re_c = 1 \times 10^7$.

M_∞	α	Buffet	k_{exp}	k_{num}
0.72	6.0	yes	0.55	0.52
0.75	4.0	yes	0.47	0.39
0.77	4.0	yes	0.44	0.45
0.80	4.0	no	0.38	-

Fig. 6. Mean pressure coefficient (left) and RMS (right) around the OAT15A coloured by angle of attack, at $M_\infty = 0.73$ and $Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$. Solid lines: CFD results; symbols: experiments of [4].

Table 4
Table of time-marching computations performed for the OAT15A aerofoil, $Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$.

M_∞	α	Buffet	St_{exp}	St_{num}
0.73	3.5	yes	0.066	0.067
0.72	3.5	yes	0.062	0.062
0.74	3.5	yes	0.074	0.071
0.73	3.1	yes	0.066	0.067
0.73	3.25	yes	0.066	0.067
0.73	3.9	yes	0.066	0.067

The computations were carried out using a 2D PANS approach with the SST model as a RANS parent. The PANS formulation was detailed in sec. 2.2. The adoption of PANS allowed for the unlocking of the flow oscillations. We believe that adopting reasonably high values of the parameter f_k ($f_k = 0.7$ here if not differently specified), a PANS formulation can help in the prediction of this class of flows where most statistical turbulence models give too high levels of eddy viscosity as stated, e.g., in [50,12].

Table 3 shows the agreement in terms of buffet frequency for different flow conditions at $Re_c = 1.0 \times 10^7$ for the NACA0012 aerofoil. Of all the conditions analysed, the 2D PANS computation was not able to reproduce the self-sustained shock oscillations at Mach number 0.8, a point that is reported to be difficult to predict, in the literature [50,54]. The improvement of the ability of turbulence models or simulation strategies to predict buffet is beyond the scope of this work, and so, the current agreement is seen as satisfactory.

Very good agreement, on the other hand, was found between PANS and experiments for the OAT15A aerofoil, while URANS simulations with the SST model led to a steady-state solution even at angles of attack well beyond the buffet onset. The distributions of the mean pressure coefficient and the root mean square around the aerofoil were in good agreement with the experiments for several angles of attack, both at pre- and post-buffet onset (see Fig. 6). Table 4 shows the comparison with the experiments in terms of Strouhal number associated with the main buffet frequency at different Mach numbers and angles of attack.

3.4. HB results

The ability of the harmonic balance method to cope with the unsteady flows developing in the aforementioned test cases is now investigated.

For buffet cases, the harmonic balance method works well and predicts the self-sustained oscillations of the shock for both configurations. Figs. 7 and 8 show the comparison between the aerodynamic loads at the $2N_H + 1$ time snapshots for different numbers of harmonics for the NACA0012 and the OAT15A aerofoils, respectively. In both cases, if at least 3 harmonics are used, the lift and drag oscillations are well captured. Figs. 10 and 9 show how in both cases, the 2D buffet motion is well predicted by means of Mach contours and the direct comparison with the TMS counterpart. The 7-mode computations shown here can capture the fundamental flow physics for both test sections, putting into evidence the interaction between shock and boundary-layer across all the phases of buffet. One period includes the creation of the shock foot separation region, merging into one separated flow region from the shock foot to the aerofoil trailing edge, the upstream shock motion with fully separated boundary layer, and the boundary layer reattachment. The same flow characterisation, although not shown here, was provided by simulations with a smaller number of harmonics ($N_H = 3, 5$).

Fig. 11 underlines some differences between the two test cases by showing the convergence of the lift coefficient against the number of iterations for the seven-mode computations. The displayed values represent the lift coefficient calculated with the solutions at the

Fig. 7. Lift (left) and drag (right) coefficients obtained with time marching simulations (TMS) and harmonic balance (HB) with different number of modes for the flow around the NACA0012 aerofoil at $Re_c = 6 \times 10^6$, $M_\infty = 0.72$ and $\alpha = 6.00$ deg.

Fig. 8. Lift (left) and drag (right) coefficients obtained with time marching simulations (TMS) and harmonic balance (HB) with different number of modes for the flow around the OAT15A aerofoil at $Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$, $M_\infty = 0.73$ and $\alpha = 3.5$ deg.

Table 5
CPU time for the time marching and harmonic balance aerofoil computations.

No. modes	CPU time [h]	Saving
NACA0012		
TMS	13.79	-
1	1.54	89%
3	4.67	66%
5	9.21	33%
7	11.77	15%
OAT15A		
TMS	16.98	-
1	1.59	91%
3	5.91	65%
5	11.56	32%
7	15.10	11%

different time instants over a buffet period. The OAT15A case (right) displays a slightly oscillating behaviour in the lift coefficient history, while the NACA0012 (left) does not. This is possibly due to the blunt trailing edge in the OAT15A geometry, and the pseudo time-stepping method used to integrate the system of equations. Nevertheless, the peak-to-peak amplitudes of these oscillations are around two orders of magnitude smaller than the corresponding mean values and, therefore, they are not seen as a problem for the buffet boundary estimation process. To avoid a wrong detection of buffet, the b coefficient in eq. (27) cannot be set to zero.

The cost comparison of Table 5 shows the net saving in CPU time with respect to the time marching simulations. In all cases, simulations were run on 8 CPUs. The CPU time considered for the time marching simulations was that required to develop the shock oscillation and reach three almost identical buffet periods. The CPU cost grows significantly with the number of harmonics but it never exceeded the TMS time.

3.5. Buffet boundary evaluation

Here, the results of the harmonic balance computations embedded in the procedure for the buffet boundary estimation are described. Following the results of the previous section, the number of harmonics should be between 3 and 5, to avoid the undersampling of the buffet period and undesired high CPU costs.

NACA0012 computations

Fig. 12, left plot, shows the differences in the buffet boundary, evaluated as explained in the previous section, between the same procedure with three and five modes for the flow around the NACA0012 aerofoil at Reynolds number of $Re_c = 6 \times 10^6$. The accuracy on the buffet onset was fixed to $\Delta\alpha = 0.2$ deg, while the increment on the Mach number to $\Delta M_\infty = 0.01$, and these parameters were kept constant across all the simulations. Here, there is little difference between the results with different numbers of harmonics. This justifies

Fig. 9. Mach number contours for the flow around the NACA0012 aerofoil computed with TMS (left) and HB (right) at different phases in a buffet period ($Re_c = 6 \times 10^6$, $M_\infty = 0.72$ and $\alpha = 6.00$ deg). From top to bottom: most downstream position, upstream moving shock, most upstream position, downstream moving shock. The dashed, black lines represent the zero-longitudinal velocity isolines.

the use the smaller number of harmonics $N_H = 3$, since no accuracy was lost by decreasing the number of modes retained, especially in the range of Mach numbers where the procedure agrees with the experiments. The estimation, compared to the experiments, provides good agreement for Mach numbers less than 0.78. Difficulties in the prediction of buffet at Mach number 0.8 have been reported in the literature [50,54]. Therefore, a reduction of the eddy viscosity was adopted by reducing the PANS parameter f_k from 0.7 to 0.6. This modification reflected in an overall early prediction of the buffet boundary. Indeed, while an improved prediction is obtained at high Mach number, the reduction of the overall eddy viscosity level causes the buffet onset to be underpredicted at lower Mach number. Moreover, the role of the b value for the unsteady buffet criterion in eq. (27) was also investigated. The two values tested were $b = 0.025, 0.05$. The adoption of a lower value of this parameter allows for a slight improvement of the prediction at lower Mach numbers (Fig. 12, right plot), giving an early prediction of the buffet onset. A lower value is also recommended to keep the estimation as conservative as possible.

Finally, the results obtained were compared with those in an earlier publication [29] using RANS-based criteria in Fig. 13. The criterion based on the C_L coefficient provided an early, although conservative, prediction of the buffet boundary, underpredicting the onset of about 1 degree for the main part of the Mach number interval considered. When coupled with the adjoint method for a faster evaluation of the boundary, the criterion gave similar results. The criterion based on the pitching moment coefficient C_M provided improved results with

Fig. 10. Mach number contours for the flow around the OAT15A aerofoil computed with TMS (left) and HB (right) at different phases in a buffet period ($Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$, $M_\infty = 0.73$ and $\alpha = 3.5$ deg). From top to bottom: most downstream position, upstream moving shock, most upstream position, downstream moving shock. The dashed, black lines represent the zero-longitudinal velocity isolines.

respect to the previous one, at least for this test case. On the other side, the application of the criterion in conjunction with the adjoint method was less accurate. Therefore, to obtain higher accuracy, the estimation process would require the computation of the steady flow solution at different flight conditions, increasing the CPU costs. The performance of the procedure proposed in this work was comparable with that of the C_M -based criterion for the first part of the Mach number interval of interest. In the second part, the inability of the adopted turbulence model to predict buffet reflected in a late buffet onset. This test case demonstrates the advantages and disadvantages of this procedure over a RANS-based one. While it improves too conservative methods based on steady computations, by accounting for the unsteadiness of buffet by means of HB computations, its performance is strongly influenced, in this case limited, by the underlying turbulence model. This latter affects, in the same way, the harmonic balance and time marching simulations, as shown in Fig. 13, where the TMS onset was pointed at selected points over the buffet boundary.

OAT15A computations

Similar computations were repeated for the OAT15A wing section. In this case, the experimental buffet onset was only known at $M_\infty = 0.72$ and 0.73 , making difficult to draw definitive conclusions for the entire interval of interest. For this test case, the harmonic

Fig. 11. History of the lift coefficient associated with different time snapshots for the HB computations around the NACA0012 (left) and OAT15A (right) wing sections.

Fig. 12. Estimated buffet boundary for the NACA0012 wing section at $Re_c = 6 \times 10^6$ for different numbers of harmonics (left), value of f_k (centre), and b (right). Experiments of [52]. RANS-based criteria results from [29].

Fig. 13. Estimated buffet boundary for the NACA0012 wing section at $Re_c = 6 \times 10^6$. Experiments of [52]. RANS-based criteria results from [29].

balance brings some improvements in the prediction of buffet (see Fig. 14), which was underpredicted by both criteria employed in Ref. [29]. To extend the validity of the provided results to a broader interval of Mach numbers, a comparison with the work of Giannelis et al. [51] was provided. In their work, a reduction of the a_1 coefficient of the SST model was adopted, and several computations, with an increment in the flight parameters of $\Delta\alpha = 0.5$ and $\Delta M_\infty = 0.01$, were carried out. The two numerical predictions are in good agreement. In the same plot, the comparison with the onset from TMS using the PANS model is also provided, showing, once again, the ability of the HB method to reproduce the results of the TMS.

Fig. 14. Estimated buffet boundary for the OAT15A wing section at $Re_c = 3 \times 10^6$. Experiments of [4]. RANS-based criteria results from [29].

4. Conclusions and future work

In this work, the ability of the harmonic balance method to deal with transonic buffet flows has been evaluated. The method aims at approximating the results of time-marching simulations through a small number of instantaneous solutions over a period of oscillation. A 2D PANS formulation was used for the time-marching computations and was accurate in predicting the main quantities associated with the oscillating motion, like fundamental frequency of oscillation and mean pressure coefficient and RMS (where available). The harmonic balance equation was run together with an adaptive frequency technique, given the lack of knowledge of the fundamental flow frequency of oscillation, which is, in turn, required to carry out harmonic balance computations. The method was tested for the vortex shedding flow around a circular cylinder at laminar conditions and provided accurate results, regardless of the initial guess of the reduced frequency and the number of harmonics adopted. The same results were obtained for flows around the NACA0012 and OAT15A aerofoil, starting from a number of harmonics equal to three. A slightly higher number of harmonics should be used if one wants to avoid the risk of undersampling the period of oscillation. In any case, when compared to time-marching simulations, the CPU cost is reduced. For the cases under consideration, a number of harmonic higher than 7 would result in CPU costs equal or higher to those of time-marching simulations. Using 3-5 harmonics, the flow physics of 2D buffet was correctly predicted in all its phases over a period of oscillation.

The harmonic balance computations were then embodied in a simple procedure for the buffet boundary estimation for the two 2D configurations. The results confirmed the noticeable decrease in the CPU cost associated with the buffet boundary characterisation with respect to time-marching simulations. As hinted by the preliminary computations performed, the algorithm is insensitive to the number of harmonics used, as long as it is sufficient to adequately sample one period of oscillation. Compared to a past work [29], where RANS-based criteria were adopted, the prediction of the buffet boundary was improved for flight conditions where the turbulence model adequately predicts the buffet onset. Unfortunately, the harmonic balance computations inherit the ability to predict flow unsteadiness from the underlying turbulence model, and fail in predicting buffet at high Mach numbers for the NACA0012 section, as happened in other works on the topic [54,50]. This clearly puts into evidence how the harmonic balance accuracy is limited by the performance of the underlying turbulence model. For the OAT15A configuration, the procedure gave a good prediction of the buffet onset compared to the limited data available.

The lack of reliability and consistency of statistical turbulence models in predicting buffet demands for the use of scale-resolving simulations, e.g. DES or even LES. Therefore, it would be worth investigating the performance of the harmonic balance method in conjunction with one of the aforementioned approaches. Nevertheless, it is reasonable to believe that the number of modes required to obtain a degree of accuracy comparable with time-marching simulations would be too high to justify the employment of a harmonic balance technique. The application of such method with formulations like SAS or PANS can be seen as a compromise in terms of costs and accuracy between URANS and DES/LES, and seems a viable option for future studies. Another task would be to assess if a harmonic balance method is still worth using for 3D flows when more accurate and resolved solutions are sought.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Andrea Petrocchi was supported by the European Union.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Fig. 15. Lift (left) and drag (right) coefficients obtained with time marching simulations (TMS) and harmonic balance (HB) with different number of modes for the flow around a laminar cylinder at $Re_D = 180$.

Fig. 16. Flow residuals history for the HB computation with 7 modes for the flow around the laminar cylinder at $Re_D = 180$.

Fig. 17. Reduced frequency history for the computation for the flow around the laminar cylinder at $Re_D = 180$ with the GBVTP method. Left: different initial values for k and $N_h = 5$; right: different number of modes and $k_0 = 0.7$.

Appendix A. Laminar circular cylinder

In this appendix, the auxiliary computations for the flow around a laminar, circular cylinder are presented. A circular cylinder at $Re_D = 180$ and $M_\infty = 0.2$ was chosen for its simplicity to assess the ability of the HB computation to recover the results of the TMS. On this case, several tests were carried out to evaluate the exactness of the adaptive frequency method to capture the right frequency of vortex shedding, corresponding to a Strouhal number $St \approx 0.19$ [55].

The computations were carried out in 2D on a grid of 256×128 cells in the tangential and radial direction, respectively, and a time step $\Delta t = 0.01D/U_\infty$, corresponding to more than one hundred steps per period of oscillation. Further refinement of the spatio-temporal grid did not lead to any significant changes in the amplitude of oscillation or the fundamental frequency.

The time marching simulation was run switching off the turbulence model. The vortex shedding was well captured and associated with a periodic oscillation of the aerodynamic coefficients. The fundamental frequency obtained, corresponding to a Strouhal number of 0.189, is in good agreement with the experimental results.

Several simulations were run to mainly investigate the exactness of the harmonic balance computation and the GBVTP method. Fig. 15, shows the comparison in terms of the drag and lift coefficients between the harmonic balance computations with different number of

harmonics and the time marching simulation. For this case, adopting a number of harmonics greater or equal to 3 the history of the aerodynamic coefficients over a period of oscillation is well replicated, showing almost no discrepancy with respect to the time marching simulation.

Fig. 16, right plot, shows the behaviour of the flow residual during the harmonic balance computation for $N_H = 7$. In this case, the GBVTP method is also used. In a similar way as for the aerofoils, the computation must be initialised by plunging the cylinder to allow the harmonic balance method to start. When the cylinder, after the initial phase, is kept still, an increase in the residual is expected because of the change applied. In the following phases, the residual kept decreasing as expected.

The GBVTP convergence towards the right value of the reduced frequency is shown in Fig. 17 for different values of the initial frequency (left plot) and number of harmonics (right plot). It must be noted that for a different number of harmonics the adaptive-frequency procedure points toward increasingly exact values of the fundamental frequency of oscillation, although more time is needed for simulations with the higher number of harmonics. The underlying reason may be the decrease in the damping coefficient ϵ_N with the increase in the number of harmonics, limiting the effect of the temporal spectral viscosity term.

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